

The Escalation of English in Morocco: From the blue to the breakthrough

Rachid ED-DALI*

Mohamed BAAQILI*¹

*English Department, Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences

Cadi Ayyad University

Morocco

Submitted by Mohamed BAAQILI on 14.08.2024.

ABSTRACT

In the present time, English is incontestably the world's lingua franca. It has become the language of the modern era and its conspicuous spread in all the vital domains of life has made it the world's global language par excellence. This state of affairs is substantially visible in many non-English-speaking countries around the globe and Morocco is no exception. As an Arabo-Amazigh country, English has remarkably, albeit deliberately, managed to permeate the Moroccan linguistic market to the detriment of French, which has always been deemed as the country's prioritized second language in the kingdom's stock of languages. This scene has urged Moroccan politicians and language planners to revisit the linguistic policy in the country aspiring for a full integration of English in the national linguistic repertoire, particularly in the educational realm. In that vein, the present article aims at delineating the spread of English in the country within three different historical eras: the pre-colonial stage, the colonial stage, and the post-colonial stage and the consequential efforts made towards its promotion.

Keywords: Educational Realm, English, Lingua Franca, Language Policy, Morocco.

1. Introduction

Today, the English language is, undeniably, the world's most spoken language par excellence with an approximate number of 1.5 billion speakers (Statista Research Department, 2023). It is the mother tongue of more than 450 million speakers in different sovereign states such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, Ireland, New Zealand, and

¹ **Corresponding author:** m.baaqili.ced@uca.ac.ma

various Islands in the Caribbean Sea and the Pacific Ocean. Besides, it is an official language in India, the Philippines, Singapore, many Sub-Saharan Countries, and some commonwealth countries as well as in plenty of world organizations such as the European Union and the United Nations to name but a few (Crystal and Potter, 2023). Moreover, English is the first choice of foreign language to be widely taught in most countries in the world. Granted this preeminence, English has inarguably earned the position of a “Global Language” (Parupalli, 2019b).

Granted such prestigious caliber, it is no surprise that accommodating this language into most countries’ linguistic policy has become a priority in order to keep up with ever-growing demands of the modern era in which English is the chief language of vital domains such as: diplomacy, trade, scientific research, technology and education. As a developing country aspiring for growth and prosperity, Moroccan authorities have also become conscious of the decisive role of English as an international language and as a key for integrating the global labor market and achieving economic development and ensuring educational advancement.

The present study endeavors to discuss the factors behind the rise of English as a global language and how it distinctively survived as a predominantly international language compared to its predecessors - Latin, Greek and Arabic - who used to be world languages back in time. Also, a brief account of how English has nowadays penetrated various domains worldwide will follow. Then, the article provides a detailed account of how the language of the Anglo-Saxons spread in the Kingdom’s linguistic market with a specific reference to the ministerial measures to the consolidation of its status and full integration in the Moroccan curriculum.

2. The Emergence of English as a World Language

Crystal (2003) alleges that for a language to gain global status, it does not necessarily have to be spoken as a first language by people in that country. A global language can be used as a first, second, or foreign language. Rather, a language becomes global only when it has a certain “role” that is acknowledged in every country. To attain this recognition, people have to give it a special place within their communities either by making it the official language in the country to be used as a medium of communication in fields like media, economy, politics, law, and education, or by prioritizing it in the country’s policy of foreign language teaching.

In opposition to the prevailing fallacy among laymen that attributes the expansion of English worldwide to the easiness of its learning, Crystal (2003) and Parimal (2013) argue that the distinct global spread of the English language is not due to the simplicity of the language structure per se which makes its acquisition relatively effortless. To substantiate their claim,

they put forth three solid arguments: (i) the English language does exceptionally possess linguistic properties that make its learning easy such as the relative lack of inflectional morphemes and honorifics as well as the absence of grammatical gender and lexical tone. Nonetheless, one should not overlook other aspects of the language that are more complex such as the amount of irregularity in its spelling system. (ii) languages that are marked by heavy use of inflections and grammatical gender (such as French and Latin) and lexical tone (like Mandarin Chinese) used to be global languages at the time. (iii) children in all cultures tend to learn their language, over relatively the same period of time, despite grammatical disparities in their languages. Therefore, global status has nothing to do with linguistic character.

In the same vein, the present-day international status of English cannot be attributed to the number of its speakers but rather to who those speakers are and how powerful they are (Faber, 2023). For instance, Latin spread as a global language during the era of the Roman Empire, not due to the high density of the Romans compared to the people they conquered but, rather, owing to their ferociously dominant military power. Even after the demise of the Roman Empire, Latin persisted as an international language in many European countries for a millennium thanks to the power of Roman Catholicism (Osobliviai, 2023). Equivalently, Greek became an international language of communication in the Middle East for over than two millenniums not because of the intellectual influences of prominent Greek scholars such as Plato and Aristotle but rather because of the fierceness of the armies of Alexander the Great (Lejeune et al., 2024). Likewise, the spread of Islam by the ruthless Moorish forces in the eighth century led to a far-reaching escalation of Arabic across North Africa and the Middle East (Salikoko, 2008).

Crystal (2003), Zagada (2019), and Winchester (2023) contend that English has reached the status of “a global language” by virtue of extrinsic factors pertaining to the “power” of its people – especially political and military power. These factors can be categorized into geo-historical and socio-cultural factors: the former pertains to the extension of the British empire which peaked towards the end of the nineteenth century taking over territories in literally every continent. This eventually led, by the middle of the twentieth century, to the adoption of English as an official or semi-official language in the newly independent states. Ergo, English is now ubiquitous in every single part of the world as the language “on which the sun doesn’t set” (Quirk & Randolph, 1985 as cited in Crystal, 2003, p. 426). Also, the emergence of America, by the outset of the nineteenth century, as a dominant economic, industrial, and military power

has added greatly to the number of English speakers all over the globe and contributed to its extension worldwide (Bharathi, 2015).

3. English in the Modern Era

Nowadays, the English language is palpably expanding and evolving into a real-world language owing to the burgeoning progress in science and technology, particularly the internet and mobile phone. Crystal (2004) argues that the production of a large proportion of online content in English accelerates its spread globally. This allegation is substantiated by recent statistics on languages most frequently used for web content by share of websites. The results reveal a sweeping dominance of 52.1% of world websites in the English language compared to 5.5% and 4.8% of web content delivered in Spanish and German respectively (Statista Research Department, 2024).

Dahan (2013) attributes the ascending status of English to its symbiotic relationship with globalization. On the one hand, English serves as lingua franca that facilitates globalization. Areas like trade with multilingual companies, diplomacy, science and technology, global media, including films, internet and television, operate mainly in English. On the other hand, living in a globalized and inter-connected world has increased the demands for English proficiency to promote educational and professional development, cross-cultural understanding and digital expansion. Devasia (2024) and Rosetta Stone (2024) acknowledge the critical role of learning foreign languages in the field of international business communication and unanimously place English on the top list of languages learnt worldwide for effective global commerce. Hence, because of the promising prospects it offers, English was merged into the school curriculum in numerous nations as a second language and pupils begin learning it at an early age (Parupally, 2019a).

In the last couple of decades, English has become very pervasive due to its heavy leverage in numerous life sectors and learning it has become an exigency for people's personal and professional prosperity. To back up this assertion, Crystal (2003, 2006), Parimal (2013), and Reddy and Mahavidyalaya (2016), among other scholars, identified several domains in which learning English is undoubtedly mandatory:

3.1. Business

English is the language used by business organizations for their international correspondence both in print and electronic media. It is the language used to carry the message across and reach an agreement with multiple companies and alliances to ultimately develop and

expand overseas. Employees with good proficiency and fluency in English can easily integrate the corporate life as they are deemed very useful for the growth of their organizations at the international level thanks to their communication skills (Niyozova, 2020).

3.2. Tourism

Success of the tourism management depends chiefly on the ability to successfully satisfy the client's needs and attain mutual understanding with international tourists. English plays a vital role in this regard since it is employed as a language of intermediacy and negotiation in areas of lodging and transportation (Al-Saadi, 2015; Abdul Zalil & Lim, 2022). Safety instructions on planes and cruises, emergency procedures in hotels, and way directions are now exhibited in English in parallel with native languages. People with good linguistic competence in English can facilely travel all around the world with the minimum likelihood of encountering communicative and cross-cultural hindrances as English is considered an international language that enjoys the status of Lingua Franca. Consequently, learning it by people who work in the tourism industry and those who wish to travel to foreign countries proves to be a priority for English is the sole medium of communication and bilateral accord regardless of linguistic and cultural discrepancies (Wilson, 2018).

3.3. Science and Technology

At the outbreak of the scientific and technological revolution at the dawn of the 20th century, there was a dire need amongst researchers and scientists from all walks of life for a common medium of communication to eventually reach a reciprocal agreement. In that regard, and granted its global status, English has been adopted as a de facto international “Lingua Franca” (Fane & Wastl, 2023). A shedload of scientific articles is now in English and the vast majority of researchers among the non-native speakers deliver their oral presentations in international symposia in English, write their manuscripts in English and correspond with their colleagues overseas via English (Brock-Utne, 2016). Therefore, not only can learning this language enable scientists and scholars to access the truly prodigious and treasured scientific literature but also allows them to communicate effectively with their peers worldwide regardless of their linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

3.4. Internet

Owing to the emergence of the British Empire and America as the world's leading economic and military forces by the dawn of the 19th century, English has truly become the world's language par excellence. It is undisputedly the language of the press, television, and

the postal and telephone communication systems as well as the electronic networks, viz., the internet. This revolutionary invention first appeared in the late 1960s in the USA as the Advanced Research Project Agency Network (ARPANET) by the American government to connect computers in different locations for the exchange of information between scientists and academics and its language was English. Later on, when people from non-English speaking countries made links to ARPANET, it was necessary for them to use English (Crystal, 2004; Flammia & Saunders, 2007).

Today, because of the revolution that the world has witnessed in the use of mobile phones, emails, and the internet, approximately 70% of the web content is in English (Kramer, 2023). Also, most students, teachers, scientists, and researchers nowadays depend largely on the internet to search for information on their subject matters whereas some others use it for amusement. Consequently, many people perceive English as the language of the internet due to the vast number of English-speaking users and the high proportion of English-built websites (Ritcher, 2024).

3.5. Education

Undoubtedly, English has earned the position of the world's Lingua Franca since the bulk of the world's knowledge in the fields of science, media, literature, business, and technology is in English. Hence, it is no surprise that many countries have made it an official language or the chief foreign language to be taught at school. The rationale behind the integration of English into a country's educational system is to render the learners linguistically proficient enough to genuinely fathom the vast knowledge available online in English. This intention will consequently enable them to keep up with the leading nations in the most vital fields of science, medicine, engineering, business, and information technology. At the tertiary level, English has been the medium of instruction in several countries starting from the 1960s. Even in countries where English is not an official language, the syllabi in fields of engineering and science are written in English. So, students who learn English as a foreign language will certainly gain more knowledge in their respective fields and eventually thrive in their personal and professional lives (Sharma & Dwivedi, 2024; Neelambaram et al., 2024).

It is worth noting, however, that despite the predominant use of English in the aforementioned domains, most nations still cling to their linguistic identity and promote multilingualism via the insertion of their local language(s) alongside English in sign boards, official documents and media content. Such approach help integrate the global world while preserving the nation's cultural idiosyncrasy.

4. The infiltration of English in the Moroccan Linguistic Character

According to recent statistics, English has incomparably earned the privilege of the world's Lingua Franca with more than 1.5 billion speakers worldwide either natively or as a second language (Statista Research Department, 2023). Indeed, it has become the prevalent language of globalization as it permeated, in one way or another, into every corner of the planet, including Morocco.

4.1. The Pre-Colonial Stage

Prior to the French and Spanish incursions, the linguistic landscape in Morocco was characterized by its simplicity (Lotfi & Noaman, 2014). Two languages used to cohabit peacefully, Arabic and Amazigh, despite the intense contact between them and the linguistic alterations it brought about. Still sporadic and limited use of English was also traced in Morocco during the pre-colonial era.

Back at that time, although English had no native speakers or learners in the country, still, its use was restricted to a few economic and diplomatic affairs with Britain and the United States of America. According to the British Embassy Rabat (2013), the first diplomatic contact with Britain dates back to the 13th century when the king of England, John son of Henry II (1167-1216), dispatched an embassy to Almohad Sultan Muhammad Al-Nassir (1199-1213) to request military support against France who took advantage of internal conflicts fueled by some rebellious barons and threatened to invade the country. In 1541, after the Portuguese withdrawal from Morocco, Britain sought to strengthen its political and economic ties with the Moroccan kingdom due to the latter's strategic geographical position. For that purpose, different treaties were signed by both parties to develop and facilitate commercial activities. Thereafter, trade expanded rapidly with English merchants being granted a special status by Moroccan authorities following strict recommendations by the Sa'adi Sultan Abd El Malek (1575-1578). The first Moroccan ambassador, Rais Merzouk Ahmed Ben Kacem, was sent by Sultan Ahmed El Mansour in 1588 during the reign of Queen Elizabeth I (1558-1603). In the mid-seventeenth century, Moroccan-British relations expanded largely with the exchange of letters of friendship and cooperation between Queen Elizabeth I and some Sa'adi Sultans via their respective ambassadors (Rogers,1991).

In the same vein, bearing witness to the noticeable infiltration of English into the Moroccan linguistic market was the Moroccan-American relations that commenced at the outset of the 18th century. In 1777, Morocco was the first country to acknowledge America's

independence (U.S. Embassy & Consulates in Morocco, n.d.). Eventually, the leader of the Alawi Dynasty, Sultan Mohammed III, issued a decree in favor of American ships to enter the Moroccan ports without any restrictions. Later in 1786, Morocco sought to further fortify her alliance with America; a desire that was crowned by the signing of a treaty of peace and friendship. To return the favor, America's recognition of Morocco's independence in 1956 was the dawn of deeper and stronger relations on a large scale (Kachoub, 2021).

4.2. The Colonial Stage

During the Protectorate, the presence of English in the Moroccan linguistic landscape dwindled due to the coexistence of Amazigh and Arabic alongside French as the ostensibly dominant and supreme language. The sole contact of English at that time was confined to some diplomatic and economic relations with Britain and America. Loutfi and Noaman (2014) traced two major stages in the history of Morocco in which English was noticeably used:

The first one is when Tangier was legally designated as an international zone by law from 1923 till 1956. Tangier's strategic geographical location as the gateway to Africa and the Mediterranean rendered it an exception in the French and Spanish occupation agenda. It was not deemed as a colony, but rather, as a "free" land jointly ruled by France, Spain, and Britain. In this heady time, Tangier was perceived as a heavenly attraction for people from different walks of life; spies, businessmen, diplomats, writers, artists, and even criminals. Therefore, English was used as a lingua franca to ensure mutual understanding in such a heterogeneous society.

The second notable event was during World War II when the Americans established three military bases in Kenitra, Tangier, and Casablanca as staging areas for bombers pointed to the Soviet Union. During that time, Moroccans became acquainted with English as they used to hear it every day from the American soldiers who settled in the major cities of Morocco, and "that event was by far the most historical link between Moroccans and English" (Ennaji, 2005, p. 115). There was a big deal of casual encounters between the Americans and Moroccans to the extent that the latter managed to virtually pick up a deluge of basic English words and expressions to ensure mutual intelligibility.

4.3. The Post-Colonial Stage

After France and Spain relinquished their protectorates in 1956 and 1958 respectively, various changes occurred in the Moroccan linguistic landscape. Unlike French and Spanish which are reminiscent of colonialism for Moroccans, English is the sole foreign language with

no colonial overtones (Errihani, 2008). Advent in science and technology along with the rapid diffusion of the internet generated an urgent need for a lingua franca that fosters global communication and caters to the ever-growing changes and demands that the world witnesses every day and, seemingly, English availed that urgency.

Accordingly, there has been a growing conviction among Moroccan language planners that the future must shift urgently from French to the adoption of English in order to make a total disruption of the country's colonial past on the one hand and, on the other hand, to keep up with the world's front runners in fields of business, economy, politics, tourism, scientific research and education as well (Belhiah, 2020). Moroccan authorities have become aware of such exigency and, thus, planned initially to "impose" English gradually into the Moroccan educational system. In that respect, Sadiqi (1991) revealed that "policy-makers in Morocco have certainly realized that international communication between Morocco and the rest of the world could not be achieved by French alone; it was realized that English is the key to communication in a very tangible sense" (p. 73).

Similarly, Hyde (1994) maintained that "in Morocco, it has been felt necessary to learn another "imposed" language: English" (p. 295). Such intention emanated from the prestigious status English has gained across nations as a means for attaining intercultural understanding, socio-economic growth, and prosperity. Along the same lines, he asserted that:

"Language nowadays deals in the image, and can be marketed and sold like any other product or service: 'speaking English is the key to employment', 'speaking English joins you to the international community', 'speaking English makes for modernity', and so forth". (p. 296)

Recent decades have witnessed a palpable proliferation in scholarly works investigating the rapid expansion of English in post-colonial Morocco. For instance, Sadiqi (1991) and Ennaji (2005), among others, have conducted exhaustive and in-depth inquiries in that regard and found out that English has gained considerable attention from Moroccan policymakers and educationalists after the independence. Although Arabic was declared as the official language of instruction and French was the "Langue Véhiculaire" – "Lingua Franca" – via which scientific subjects were taught, English was one of the foreign languages students optionally chose to learn in senior high schools along with Spanish, German and Italian and, surprisingly enough, it is often chosen by students as their favorite foreign language.

To gratify the students' inclinations towards English over the other options, and being conscious of the distinguished position this language enjoys globally, Moroccan authorities and language planners have allotted a number of week-hours for the teaching of English in secondary schools: three hours for science streams, six for humanities and eight for the Special English classes which are basically geared towards the pupils who are exceptionally brilliant in English (Elfatihi, 2019).

A consequence of this action led to a wider spread of English at the level of higher education. According to statistics by Sadiqi (1991), there were only two departments of English in the early seventies (Fes and Rabat) compared to eleven a couple of decades later. This rise of departments of English in Moroccan universities resulted in a surge in the number of university graduates. Accordingly, the population of teachers of English in senior high schools jumped noticeably from 25 Moroccan teachers in 1967 to 276 in 1977 to over 3000 in 1999 (Ennaji, 2005). In order to cater for the training of these teachers, two official institutions were inaugurated: the "Ecole Normale Supérieure" – "Teachers' Training College" – in Rabat and Meknès and "Centre Pédagogique Régional" – "Regional Center of Pedagogy" – in Fes.

Privately sponsored educational institutions have also flourished in Morocco with the aim of optimizing the teaching of English and yielding a quality learning environment. Of these, one must mention the opening of Al Akhawayn University in 1995 in Ifran; the first Anglophone university in Morocco, the American Language Center and its branches all over Morocco, the British Council in Rabat and Casablanca in addition to the inception of American schools in Rabat, Tangier and Marrakech (Loutfi & Noamane, 2014). Likewise, another institution that is worthy of note is AMIDEAST; a leading American non-profit organization that was founded in Rabat in 1951 aspiring to bind the two countries together – Morocco and America. AMIDEAST focused on promoting the spread of English in the country at the expense of its rival, France, by fostering respect and mutual understanding between both nations through life-changing opportunities for education and cultural exchanges in the form of grants and scholarships (About Amideast | Morocco, n.d.). Over the years, all these institutions, in addition to dozens of English language centers in the private sector have been promulgating English in this country.

Inconvertibly, the proliferation of English language institutes and centers arose from the nation's keen awareness of the exalted position of English as the language of globalization. His Majesty King Mohamed 6th urged the authorities, in his speech on the occasion of the 60th anniversary of the Revolution of the King and the People, to revisit the educational language

policy to ultimately respond to the growing and onerous demands of the modern era. In that respect, His Majesty declared, as cited in Belhiah and Belkassem (2016), that:

The education sector is facing many difficulties and problems. They are mostly due to the adoption of some syllabi and curricula that do not tally with the requirements of the job market. Another reason has to do with the disruptions caused by changing the language of instruction from Arabic, at the primary and secondary levels, to some foreign languages, for the teaching of scientific and technical subjects in higher education. Accordingly, students must be provided with the necessary linguistic skills so that they may fully benefit from training courses. Moroccans should, therefore, be encouraged to learn and master foreign languages. (p. 215)

This excerpt, alongside other official documents such as The Moroccan National Charter (1999), The Strategic Vision (2015-2030), The Roadmap for Education System Reform (2022-2026), and The Framework Law 17.51 - which all aim, among other objectives, at facilitating access to foreign languages at an early age, have promptly exhorted language planners and decision-makers, all along the past few years, to undertake serious endeavors to promote the status of English in the country and integrate it into the Moroccan linguistic market. In 2014, the ex-minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Lahcen Daoudi (2012-2016), issued a ministerial circular in which he stipulated the mastery of English for students majoring in engineering and medical studies before obtaining their doctorate and also for Moroccan university professor candidates as one of the recruiting criteria, especially in the domains of health, management, science, technology, and economics. In addition to that, Daoudi called for the gradual replacement of French with English as the primary language of instruction in higher education and preparatory classes starting in September 2017. In many of his official meetings, he declared that English is the language of scientific research and technological advance par excellence. During his visit to Ibnou Zohr University in Agadir, he once stated straightforwardly; albeit a bit harshly, that “a student who does not master English should dig his/her own grave” (Bouziane & Saoudi, 2021, p. 188). He avowed that the rationale behind this decision lies in the fact that having a good command of the English language provides promising prospects to promote scientific research in universities, and affords university graduates better opportunities to integrate the labor market.

During his term as minister of Higher Education, Vocational Training, and Scientific Research (2018 – 2021), Said Amzazi has taken favorable actions, too. He established a cooperation with the American Ambassador to Morocco, David Fischer, which mainly sought

to promote the Moroccan educational system via the implementation of several projects. This collaboration aims, inter alia, to provide training for Moroccan English teachers in order to integrate the language progressively into primary schools' curricula in the near future (Hatim, 2020).

Probably the most audacious and acclaimed action that gave a boost to the presence of English in higher education is attributed to Driss Ouaouicha, Minister Delegate to Said Amzazi in Charge of Higher Education and Scientific Research. Ouaouicha, a PhD holder from an American University and a former Dean, vice-President, and President of Al Akhawayn University in Ifrane which has adopted English as a medium of instruction since its creation in 1995, announced that, by the onset of the academic year 2020 – 2021, the Moroccan higher education systems will substitute the three-year Licence system adopted by Francophone countries with the four-year Anglo-Saxon model: Bachelor program. In this reform, to echo Bouziane and Saoudi (2021), “English is taught for four semesters to all university students in lieu of the Licence system which abolished English at the tertiary level and maintained the dominance of French” (p. 190).

Because of the professional opportunities it offers, English continued gaining momentum in Morocco to the detriment of its rival: France. On May 2023, Chakib Benmoussa, minister of National Education, Preschool, and Sports followed in the footsteps of his predecessors and launched a project that will further boost the presence of English in the country so as to cater to the new needs of young Moroccans. Practically, he issued a circular calling for the thorough spread of English in middle schools by the school year 2025-2026. This plan will be implemented progressively in a balanced way. During the 2023-2024 school year, English will be introduced to first-year students with a coverage rate of 10 % and 50 % for second-year classes. In the following academic year, the scope of coverage will be broadened to reach 50 % in the first year and 100 % in the second year. By 2025-2026, English will be thoroughly integrated into the syllabi of the three levels in this cycle (Zouiten, 2023). According to Mohamed Zerouali, director of programs at the Ministry of Education, this initiative aims at providing equal opportunities to students from public and private schools, where English is already taught in early grades. Besides, the escalation of English will encourage cultural exchange and, thus, help young people cultivate their cross-cultural competence and global connectivity (Arredondas, 2023).

Furthermore, on May 30th, 2024, the Casablanca-Settat Regional Academy for Education and Training announced a pilot program to introduce the teaching of the English

language in the region's primary schools' sixth grade starting from the academic year 2024/2025. According to the ministerial memorandum by the academy, this operation will be tested in a limited manner. That is, it will not include all the primary schools in the region but randomly selected ones to assess their feasibility and efficiency before generalizing it (El Masaiti, 2024). This experiment stands as an endeavor to compensate for the challenges faced when introducing English-language science courses owing to insufficient language proficiency amongst students, thus, further fostering their linguistic competence in English as the language of the modern era. This initiative aligns with the Moroccan Constitution's emphasis on foreign language learning for global engagement and cultural exchange alongside The Roadmap for Education System Reform (2022-2026), The Framework Law 17.51, and the ministerial note (030x23) about the teaching of English in Moroccan middle schools which all ultimately aim at promoting linguistic diversity in the kingdom, fostering Students' linguistic proficiency at an early age to enable them to integrate the labor market readily.

5. Conclusion

This article aimed at overviewing the spread of the English language. Surely, the linguistic situation in Morocco is a complex one given the multitude of languages spoken all over the kingdom: Arabic, Amazigh, French, Spanish and English. Today, French still remains predominant in higher education and in the private sectors, Arabic has been consolidated through the Arabization policy, and Amazigh has been introduced in primary schools and penetrated the media industry, too. Regarding English, even though it is a newcomer in Morocco, it is making noticeable inroads in the country, infiltrating into the most vital spheres of life owing to educational reforms, globalization and economic growth. In concrete terms, English has become a vital means of communication with international companies and in the tourism industry, its presence in private and public higher educational institutions as a compulsory subject reflects its importance as a prerequisite for accessing the global labor market and the proliferation of English-language media including online content, podcasts and radio stations are all testimonials of this language's steady, albeit slow, penetration into various critical spheres in Morocco.

Sadiqi (1991) lists four factors behind the very noticeable spread of English in Morocco. First, since independence, the policy of education adopted by language planners and decision-makers has been supportive of English. This policy has materialized into various initiatives like the recruitment of British and American teachers, the inception of Al-Akhawayne University in Ifran, and the regular organization of summer schools, pedagogical meetings, and in-service

training for the benefit of Moroccan teachers of English. Second, the emergence of English as the world's lingua franca is widely used internationally in fields such as commerce, diplomacy, tourism, and finance. Accordingly, the emphasis on English is stirred by the country's firm aspiration to access resources and opportunities around the world. Third, Moroccans hold positive sentiments towards English as being very useful for the future of Morocco, and fourth, the absence of any association between English and colonialism in Morocco.

The accelerated growth in information technology, especially satellite television and the internet has rendered English even more popular in the country compared to French which used to be the language of the elite and social prestige. According to an exhaustive survey conducted by the British Council (2021), the vast majority of Moroccan youth regard English as vital for unlocking educational, professional, and cultural opportunities. Likewise, the same investigation revealed that 40% of Moroccan youth consider English to be the most important language for prosperity and socio-economic development, compared to 10% who consider French, conventionally the language of the kingdom's elites, to be more important than its challenger.

Thus, granted its popularity and superiority, learning English has become one of the major priorities of governments, institutions, and individuals. Being able to communicate convincingly and eloquently in the spoken form or through composition in English is undoubtedly a prerogative and learning it is assuredly an urgency.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of statement.

About the Authors

Rachid Ed-dali is professor of Applied Linguistics at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences and head of the English Department. For over than a decade, Dr, Ed-dali has been teaching English language across different levels ranging from Secondary Education, Vocational Higher Education to Mainstream Higher Education. His expertise and passion for the domain of academia were materialized in prolific publications in Translation, Media Studies, Discourse Analysis, English Language Teaching/Learning and English for Specific Purposes.

Mohamed BAAQILI is a doctoral student at the Faculty of Letters and Human Sciences, an EFL High School teacher and a freelance translator. His main areas of interest include English language Teaching, Cross-cultural Communication, Translation, Gender Studies and Applied Linguistics.

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